

Innovation of environmental friendly agricultural technology supporting sustainable food self-sufficiency environmental risk assessment principles

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**Innovation of Environmental Friendly Agricultural Technology Supporting Sustainable Food Self-Sufficiency
Environmental Risk Assessment Principles**

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What is **Risk Assessment / Risk Management?**

Central elements of risk assessment/ risk management:

- ▣ **Risk assessment**
 - ▣ **Hazard/Toxicity**
 - ▣ **Exposure**
 - ▣ **Risk characterisation**
- ▣ **Risk management**
 - ▣ **Risk mitigation**
 - ▣ **Benefit analysis**

! Consideration of all elements is important

Hazard vs. Risk in Daily Life

LETHAL DOSES OF COMMON CHEMICALS

LD₅₀
LD₅₀ stands for 'median lethal dose', and is defined as the amount of a substance required to kill 50% of a test population of animals, expressed in mg per kg of body weight. Human LD₅₀ values are calculated from these tests. For ethical reasons, tests on animals to determine LD₅₀ are being phased out in favour of other methods.

The figures provided below are median lethal doses, and are rough averages for a body weight of 75kg, when the amount specified is taken all at once. Actual figures will vary depending on physical and medical condition.

WATER
6 LITRES

CAFFEINE
118 COFFEES
1 coffee = approx. 0.08g of caffeine

"The Dose makes the Poison"
(Paracelsus, 1493-1541)

ALCOHOL
13 SHOTS
Wine (1 shot = 45ml 40% ABV)

Pesticides Hazard
 Persistent (DT 50)
 High LD50
Risk?
 => Depends on the Dose / Use Rate!

Elements of Risk Assessment?

<p>Measure of hazard (toxicity or effect)</p> <p>Questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ What happens with the substance in the environment and or used by man? ■ Which amounts can be found? ■ Which ways of exposure can occur? <p style="text-align: center; background-color: #e91e63; color: white; padding: 5px;">Variable according to use pattern, local conditions ...</p>	
<p>The risk assessment integrates both toxicity and exposure data.</p>	

Risk Assessment Principle

Key concepts

- Risk = Hazard x Exposure
- At its simplest:
Exposure < Hazard = No Risk
Therefore:
(Exposure / Hazard < 1) =
No Risk

! Hazard may be referred to as „toxicity“ or „effects“
Effect Study (LC50 / NOEC)

Risk quotients / ratios

Risk Quotient

$$RQ = \frac{\text{Exposure}}{\text{Toxicity (e.g. LD}_{50}\text{)}}$$

Small numbers indicate safety

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Exposure Assessment – Soil

Leaching Pathway

- Soil Exposure relates to
- Dose rate
 - Application timing, Cropping stage / interception
 - E-fate parameters: i. e. soil degradation (DT 50)

! Potential Exposure EEC / PEC
Environmental Exposure Concentrations (EEC) OR
Predicted Environmental Concentrations (PEC)

Exposure

PEC Soil Single Application

$$PEC_{soil} = \frac{\text{Dose - Interception}}{\text{Soil (depth, Bulk Density)}}$$

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Exposure

Risk Assessment Summary

Hands On Training of ERA

Regulatory Risk Assessment Soil

Ecological risk assessment as proposed by FAO (1989)

Outlook

- Risk Assessment is science based regulatory decision making used across industries (insurance, pharma) and continents conceptualized by FAO 1989
- Risk Assessment is Easy! $RQ = \text{Use Pattern} \& \text{DT50} / \text{Effect Study}$
- Risk assessment allows to determine actual safety of a product by considering both hazard and exposure
- DT50 is not necessarily the most critical parameter
- Simple **hazard criteria** or **persistence cutoff** criteria may lead to both **over or under estimation of risk** as they do **not account** for actual **exposure (use / application)**